

2 **Depth-stratified modelling improves hyperspectral prediction of** 3 **soil organic carbon content: a comparison with integrated** 4 **modelling in the Loess Plateau, China**

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11 **Abstract**

12 Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a key indicator of soil fertility and a major component of the terrestrial
13 carbon cycle, and rapid hyperspectral prediction of SOC has become increasingly important for
14 precision agriculture and regional carbon monitoring. The accuracy of such hyperspectral predictions,
15 however, may depend on soil depth because the spectral signal of SOC varies systematically with
16 depth-related differences in carbon composition, soil texture and water content. Here we collected 388
17 soil samples from four depth layers (0–20, 20–40, 40–60 and 60–80 cm) at 97 sampling sites in a
18 Loess Plateau cropland in Changzhi, Shanxi Province, China. Reflectance spectra (350–2500 nm)
19 were measured with an ASD FieldSpec 4 spectrometer under controlled laboratory conditions. Raw
20 spectra were denoised using a Savitzky–Golay filter and resampled at 10 nm intervals. The Kennard–
21 Stone algorithm partitioned the data into calibration and validation sets at a 2:1 ratio, and bands with
22 statistically significant Pearson correlations with SOC ($p<0.05$) were retained for modelling. We
23 compared three modelling approaches – partial least squares regression (PLSR), grid search support
24 vector regression (GRID-SVR) and particle swarm optimization-based support vector regression
25 (PSO-SVR) – under two strategies: a depth-specific (single-layer) strategy and a fully integrated
26 strategy that pooled all depths. None of the single-layer models reached a residual predictive deviation
27 (RPD) above 1.4, mainly because the within-layer coefficients of variation were small (19.5 %–
28 27.3 %). The integrated PSO-SVR model achieved validation $R^2=0.760$, RMSE=1.496 g kg⁻¹ and
29 RPD=2.051, satisfying the criterion for excellent prediction. When the validation predictions of the
30 four single-layer PSO-SVR models were merged, the overall accuracy ($R^2=0.830$, RMSE=1.312 g
31 kg⁻¹, RPD=2.434) exceeded that of the integrated model. The findings imply that, although individual
32 single-depth models may underperform in narrow-range data, depth-stratified modelling followed by
33 prediction merging is a useful strategy for improving overall accuracy of hyperspectral SOC inversion.
34 The framework is potentially applicable to other soil attributes that show strong vertical heterogeneity.

35 **Keywords.** soil organic carbon; hyperspectral remote sensing; particle swarm optimization; support
36 vector regression; soil depth; Loess Plateau

37 Soil organic carbon content can be measured rapidly using reflectance spectroscopy, but accuracy
38 often suffers when carbon variation within a sample set is low. Using 388 soil samples from four
39 depths in the Loess Plateau of China, we show that modelling each depth separately and then merging
40 the predictions yields more accurate carbon estimates than modelling all depths together, even though
41 individual depth models perform poorly. This depth-stratified approach offers a practical route to
42 improved hyperspectral soil monitoring.

43 **1 Introduction**

44 Soil organic carbon (SOC) is one of the most important chemical constituents of soils and a key
45 indicator of soil fertility and quality (Huang and Xu, 2010). As a critical component of the global
46 carbon cycle, the soil organic carbon pool is approximately two to three times the size of the
47 atmospheric carbon pool, and even small changes in soil carbon stocks can significantly affect
48 atmospheric CO₂ concentration and global climate (Lal, 2004). Accurate and rapid quantification of
49 SOC content is therefore essential for precision agricultural management, soil carbon sink assessment
50 and regional ecological protection.

51 Traditional methods for determining SOC content, such as the potassium dichromate oxidation
52 method and elemental analysis, are widely used because of their high accuracy (Bao, 1999). However,
53 these methods involve complex sample preparation, large reagent consumption and long analytical
54 cycles, and are therefore unsuitable for the rapid, high-density monitoring of soil nutrients at large
55 spatial scales (Zhou and Gong, 1996). Soils also display strong spatial variability, so that small
56 sample numbers cannot reliably represent the regional distribution of soil properties; achieving
57 accurate spatial coverage typically requires large sampling efforts (Zhou and Gong, 1996), which
58 further increases the cost of conventional analyses.

59 Hyperspectral remote sensing, with its high spectral resolution (typically at the nanometre scale) and
60 rich continuous spectral information, provides a promising alternative for the rapid, non-destructive
61 determination of soil attributes (Ben-Dor and Banin, 1995; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006). Soil organic
62 carbon possesses characteristic absorptions in the visible–near-infrared region (350–2500 nm),
63 including a general reflectance decrease in the visible (400–700 nm) caused by the dark colour of
64 organic matter and overtones and combinations of C–H, O–H and N–H bonds in the near-infrared
65 region (Shi, 2014; Stenberg et al., 2010). These features enable the construction of quantitative
66 hyperspectral prediction models for SOC (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006; Stevens et al., 2013; Nocita et
67 al., 2015), which have been applied in precision agriculture, soil environmental monitoring and
68 carbon cycling research (Peng et al., 2019; Angelopoulou et al., 2019).

69 Among the modelling methods commonly used for SOC inversion, partial least squares regression
70 (PLSR) and support vector regression (SVR) are the most widely adopted (Cui et al., 2017; Conforti

71 et al., 2013; Stenberg et al., 2010). PLSR, introduced by Wold et al. (2001), combines the strengths of
72 principal component analysis, canonical correlation analysis and multiple linear regression, and can
73 perform dimensionality reduction while preserving maximum correlation between predictors and
74 response, making it well suited to situations where the number of predictors greatly exceeds the
75 number of samples and where predictors are highly collinear (Wang, 1999; Geladi and Kowalski,
76 1986). Several previous studies confirm the effectiveness of PLSR for SOC prediction in alpine
77 grassland (Cui et al., 2017), eroded soils in southern Italy (Conforti et al., 2013) and Chinese cropland
78 (Hong et al., 2015). However, the relationship between SOC and reflectance is rarely strictly linear,
79 often containing important non-linear components (Li, 2012). SVR, originally proposed by Vapnik
80 (1995), is a non-linear regression method built on statistical learning theory and the principle of
81 structural risk minimization (Wang and Men, 2014). By mapping samples to a high-dimensional
82 feature space through a kernel function, SVR provides good generalization performance even with
83 limited training data (Vapnik, 1995; Wang and Men, 2014). Both Yu (2014) and Wang (2014)
84 confirmed the suitability of SVR for near-infrared spectral analysis of wood and forest soils,
85 respectively.

86 In SVR models, the choice of the kernel parameter γ and the penalty factor C strongly affects
87 performance (Wang and Men, 2014); manual parameter selection is time-consuming and often
88 suboptimal (Qu et al., 2015), which has motivated the adoption of automatic optimization methods.
89 Grid search (GRID) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) are two widely used strategies (Kennedy
90 and Eberhart, 1995; Qu et al., 2015). Grid search evaluates parameter combinations on a predefined
91 regular grid using cross-validation, but is sensitive to step size and search range (Qu et al., 2015). PSO,
92 introduced by Kennedy and Eberhart (1995), mimics the foraging behaviour of bird flocks: individual
93 candidate solutions (particles) move through parameter space by combining their personal best with
94 the global best of the swarm, achieving fast convergence with few tuning parameters (Zhao and Deng,
95 2015; Wang and Wu, 2008). Chen et al. (2019) used PSO to optimize PLSR for heavy-metal mapping
96 in reclaimed soils; (Zou et al., 2019) reported a 0.19 increase in coefficient of determination when
97 PSO-optimized neural networks were used for SOM prediction; and (Tan et al., 2015) applied PSO-
98 SVR to mining-area soils and confirmed the advantage of PSO over grid search.

99 In addition to the choice of modelling method, the intrinsic attributes of the sample set also strongly
100 influence model performance. Most existing studies have focused on the effects of soil type and land
101 use type (Zhang et al., 2009; Xue et al., 2014; Jiang et al., 2016; Li et al., 2019a; Wu and Zhang,
102 2016). Zhang et al. (2009) compared spectral characteristics of different soil types and concluded that
103 type-specific spectra may affect modelling accuracy; (Liu et al., 2012a) examined the effect of
104 spectral resolution on SOM modelling in black soils. For land use, (Jiang et al., 2016) studied
105 hyperspectral inversion of soil nutrients across cover types in the Ebinur Lake watershed, (Xue et al.,
106 2014) compared visible–near-infrared inversion of SOM across different land uses, and (Guo et al.,

107 2020) built type-specific SOC models for forest, cropland and orchard soils and found that merged
108 single-type PSO-SVR predictions outperformed an integrated model, providing a strong case for
109 stratified modelling. Stevens et al. (2013) showed at the European scale that land use influences both
110 the absolute SOC content and its vertical distribution, while (Nocita et al., 2015) concluded that
111 appropriate sample stratification can simultaneously preserve spectral throughput and improve
112 accuracy. Vohland et al. (2014) compared multiple variable-selection techniques (CARS, SPA,
113 genetic algorithms) for Vis–NIR–MIR soil property prediction and found that careful feature selection
114 combined with sample grouping is decisive for model quality. Together, these studies demonstrate
115 that pre-grouping samples according to intrinsic differences – whether soil type, land use, spatial
116 position or, as we will argue here, soil depth – is an effective strategy for improving hyperspectral
117 inversion of SOC.

118 In contrast to the substantial literature on soil type and land use, the effect of soil depth on
119 hyperspectral SOC inversion remains comparatively poorly explored. SOC content generally
120 decreases with depth (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000; Liang and Chen, 2015; Hobbey et al., 2015), and
121 the composition and degree of humification of organic carbon also differ vertically (Jobbágy and
122 Jackson, 2000): surface horizons are dominated by fresh plant- and animal-derived decomposition
123 products, while deeper horizons contain a higher proportion of stable, well-humified organic matter.
124 Mineralogy, particle-size distribution and water content can also vary with depth (Li et al., 2019a;
125 Cambardella et al., 1994), all of which influence soil spectral reflectance (Shi, 2014; Peng et al., 2013)
126 and may therefore affect SOC inversion models. The comprehensive review of Jobbágy and Jackson
127 (2000) showed that the vertical distribution of SOC differs substantially among global ecosystems,
128 and that this vertical heterogeneity may strongly affect spectroscopic prediction. Despite this, few
129 studies have systematically examined the impact of soil depth on hyperspectral SOC models or
130 compared depth-stratified with integrated modelling strategies.

131 Here, we collected 388 soil samples from four depth layers (0–20, 20–40, 40–60 and 60–80 cm) at
132 sites in Changzhi, Shanxi Province, on the eastern margin of the Loess Plateau, and applied the
133 methodological framework of Guo et al. (2020) to soil depth in place of land use type. We employed
134 PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR to construct both depth-specific (single-layer) and integrated (all-
135 depths-pooled) prediction models, and compared the merged predictions of single-layer models with
136 the integrated model. The objectives of this work are: (i) to quantify how soil depth affects the
137 accuracy of hyperspectral SOC inversion; (ii) to compare the performance of PLSR, GRID-SVR and
138 PSO-SVR under different modelling strategies; and (iii) to evaluate the relative merits of depth-
139 stratified and integrated modelling, with a view to providing methodological guidance for
140 hyperspectral SOC monitoring at multiple depths.

141 **2 Materials and methods**

142 2.1 Study area

143

144 *Figure 1. Location of the study area and distribution of soil sampling sites. (a) Location of Shanxi Province in*
145 *China; (b) the Changzhi region within Shanxi Province; (c) digital elevation model and 97 sampling sites in the*
146 *study area.*

147 The study area is located in the Changzhi region of Shanxi Province, China (Fig. 1), on the western
148 slope of the Taihang Mountains and the eastern margin of the Loess Plateau. The climate is temperate
149 semi-humid continental monsoon, with mean annual temperatures of 8.6–10.0 °C and mean annual
150 precipitation of 550–660 mm, concentrated mainly between July and September (Yang et al., 2004).
151 Topography is dominated by mountains, hills and basins, with elevations of 800–1500 m. Soils are
152 mostly cinnamon soils (Cambisols) and brown soils (Luvisols). Agriculture is dominated by rainfed
153 cropland, with wheat and maize as the main crops. The area is representative of the Loess Plateau,
154 where SOC content is jointly influenced by topography, land use and tillage management (Wang et al.,
155 2009; Yang et al., 2004). Compared with the red soils of southern China (Zhao and Yang, 2018; Cao,
156 1964) and the black soils of the northeast (Liu et al., 2012a; Liu et al., 2008), SOC contents in the
157 Loess Plateau are generally lower and show pronounced vertical differentiation (Yang et al., 2004;
158 Xie et al., 2004).

159 2.2 Sample collection and SOC determination

160 Sampling sites were established across the study area following a uniform spatial distribution based
161 on field reconnaissance. At each site, samples were collected from four depth layers: 0–20, 20–40,
162 40–60 and 60–80 cm. Plant residues and stones at the surface were removed prior to sampling, and
163 approximately 500 g of soil was collected at each depth. Samples were air-dried at ambient
164 temperature in the laboratory, with plant roots, gravel and other contaminants removed, then ground
165 and passed through a 2 mm nylon sieve (Bao, 1999). Each sample was split into two subsamples: one
166 for laboratory spectral measurement and one for SOC determination by the potassium dichromate
167 external-heating method (Bao, 1999). After quality-control screening, 97 samples were retained for
168 each of the four depth layers, yielding 388 samples in total. The choice of 0–20 cm increments
169 balances representativeness of typical plough-layer subdivisions with practical sampling effort and is
170 consistent with vertical SOC investigations across global croplands (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000;
171 Liang and Chen, 2015; Hobley et al., 2015).

172 **2.3 Methodological framework**

173 The overall workflow (Fig. 2) consists of four stages: (i) data acquisition; (ii) spectral preprocessing;
174 (iii) modelling; and (iv) evaluation and selection. In the data acquisition stage, 388 soil samples were
175 collected from four depths, their SOC content was determined by the potassium dichromate method
176 (Bao, 1999; Guo et al., 2020), and reflectance spectra were measured with an ASD FieldSpec 4
177 spectrometer (Ben-Dor and Banin, 1995; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006; Shi, 2014). In preprocessing,
178 raw spectra were splice-corrected, edge bands were removed, a five-point Savitzky–Golay filter was
179 applied, and spectra were resampled at 10 nm intervals, yielding 206 retained bands (Savitzky and
180 Golay, 1964; Shen et al., 2009). In modelling, the Kennard–Stone algorithm partitioned each data set
181 into calibration and validation subsets at a 2:1 ratio (Kennard and Stone, 1969), and bands passing a
182 Pearson correlation significance test ($p < 0.05$) were retained as sensitive bands (Guo et al., 2020;
183 Vohland et al., 2014). Three regression methods – PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR – were applied
184 under two strategies: a single-layer strategy (separate models for each depth) and an integrated
185 strategy (all depths pooled) (Wold et al., 2001; Vapnik, 1995; Wang and Men, 2014; Kennedy and
186 Eberhart, 1995; Zhao and Deng, 2015; Tan et al., 2015; Zou et al., 2019; Qu et al., 2015). In
187 evaluation, coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean squared error (RMSE) and residual predictive
188 deviation (RPD) were used to compare model performance (O'Rourke and Holden, 2012; Shi et al.,
189 2014), and the merged predictions of the four single-layer models were compared with the integrated
190 model to determine the best strategy (Guo et al., 2020; Stenberg et al., 2010).

191 **2.4 Spectral measurement and preprocessing**

192

193 *Figure 2. Methodological framework of the study, comprising four stages: data acquisition, spectral*
 194 *preprocessing, modelling and evaluation.*

195 Soil spectral reflectance was measured in a dark laboratory using an ASD FieldSpec 4 spectrometer
 196 (Analytical Spectral Devices, Boulder, USA). The instrument covers 350–2500 nm with a spectral
 197 resolution of 3 nm in the visible–near-infrared range (350–1000 nm) and 8 nm in the shortwave-
 198 infrared range (1000–2500 nm), and a sampling interval of 1 nm, for a total of 2151 bands (Shi, 2014).
 199 Air-dried samples were placed in black sample dishes, pressed flat and presented to the MugLite
 200 contact probe with its internal light source. The spectrometer was calibrated against a Spectralon
 201 white reference panel (reflectance >99 %) before each set of measurements, and each sample was
 202 scanned five times; the arithmetic mean of the five replicate spectra was used as the final reflectance.

203 Preprocessing followed the procedure described by (Guo et al., 2020): (i) ViewSpec Pro software was
 204 used to correct detector splice artefacts; (ii) edge bands strongly affected by noise were removed and
 205 the range 400–2450 nm was retained (Guo et al., 2020; Sun and Li, 2018); (iii) a five-point Savitzky–
 206 Golay filter was applied to suppress high-frequency noise while preserving spectral features (Savitzky
 207 and Golay, 1964); and (iv) linear interpolation was used to resample the spectra at 10 nm intervals,
 208 reducing the data from 2051 to 206 bands. The resulting reflectance vectors of 206 bands per sample
 209 were the inputs to all subsequent analyses.

210 2.5 Sample set partitioning

211 The Kennard–Stone (K-S) algorithm (Kennard and Stone, 1969) was used to partition samples into
 212 calibration and validation sets at a 2:1 ratio based on Euclidean distance in spectral space. The K-S
 213 algorithm is widely used in spectroscopic analysis: it iteratively selects the sample farthest in feature

214 space from the already-selected set, ensuring even coverage by the calibration set. The procedure was:
215 (i) compute the pairwise Euclidean distance matrix; (ii) select the two most distant samples as the
216 initial calibration set; (iii) for each remaining sample, compute its minimum distance to the calibration
217 set; (iv) add the sample with the largest minimum distance to the calibration set; (v) repeat (iii)–(iv)
218 until the desired calibration size is reached. For the single-layer strategy, each depth was partitioned
219 independently (65 calibration and 32 validation samples per depth); for the integrated strategy, all 388
220 samples were pooled and partitioned together (259 calibration and 129 validation samples).

221 **2.6 Sensitive band selection**

222 To improve modelling efficiency and stability, sensitive bands were selected by Pearson correlation
223 analysis (Guo et al., 2020). For each band, the linear correlation between calibration-set SOC content
224 and reflectance was computed and tested for significance using *t*-statistics. Bands passing the
225 significance test ($p < 0.05$) were retained as sensitive bands. This procedure reduces redundancy,
226 mitigates multicollinearity and improves generalization (Vohland et al., 2014). Where fewer than two
227 bands passed the test (Sect. 3.3), all 206 bands were used to ensure that the model could still be fitted.

228 **2.7 Modelling methods**

229 **2.7.1 Partial least squares regression (PLSR)**

230 PLSR is a multivariate statistical method introduced by Herman Wold in the 1960s (Wang, 1999;
231 Wold et al., 2001) that combines the strengths of principal component analysis, canonical correlation
232 analysis and multiple linear regression. In PLSR, latent components are extracted from both the
233 predictor matrix X and the response matrix Y such that each component maximizes both the explained
234 variance within X and Y and the correlation between the X - and Y -components (Geladi and Kowalski,
235 1986). This dual optimization makes PLSR particularly well suited to "large p , small n " problems
236 with strong multicollinearity – the standard situation in hyperspectral analysis (Wang, 1999; Hong et
237 al., 2015).

238 The number of latent variables is the key parameter of PLSR: too few causes underfitting and too
239 many introduces noise (Wold et al., 2001). We used leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV) on the
240 calibration set to select the number of latent variables that minimized the cross-validated root mean
241 squared error of prediction, with a maximum of 20 candidates and not exceeding the number of
242 calibration samples minus two or the number of bands, whichever was smaller.

243 **2.7.2 Grid search-based support vector regression (GRID-SVR)**

244 Support vector machines (SVMs), introduced by Vapnik (1995), originated as classifiers and were
245 later extended to regression as SVR (Wang and Men, 2014). SVR maps input samples non-linearly
246 into a high-dimensional feature space via a kernel function and finds a hyperplane that minimizes the

247 ϵ -insensitive loss over the training set (Vapnik, 1995). SVR has been applied across diverse fields
 248 ranging from soil spectroscopy (Vapnik, 1995; Wang and Men, 2014) and chemometrics to
 249 mechanical-system modelling (Xu et al., 2013). We used the radial basis function (RBF) kernel
 250 (Cristianini et al., 2002):

251
$$K(x^*, x'^*) = \exp(-\gamma \|x^* - x'^*\|^2) \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

252 where γ controls the kernel width: larger γ produces a sharper kernel and a more flexible model
 253 (Cristianini et al., 2002; Yang et al., 2015). The penalty C controls the cost of points lying outside the
 254 ϵ -tube; larger C fits the training data more tightly, but excessive C may cause overfitting (Wang and
 255 Men, 2014).

256 Grid search (GRID) (Qu et al., 2015) evaluates C and γ on a regular logarithmic grid using cross-
 257 validation. We set the search range to $C \in [10^{-2}, 10^4]$ and $\gamma \in [10^{-4}, 10^1]$, evenly spaced on a
 258 logarithmic scale with 13 and 12 candidate values respectively (156 combinations in total). Each
 259 combination was assessed by five-fold cross-validation on the calibration set, and the combination
 260 with the highest validation R^2 was selected.

261 **2.7.3 Particle swarm optimization-based support vector regression (PSO-SVR)**

262 PSO is a swarm intelligence method introduced by Kennedy and Eberhart (1995) inspired by the
 263 foraging behaviour of bird flocks (Zhao and Deng, 2015). Each particle represents a candidate
 264 solution in parameter space and updates its velocity and position based on its individual best position
 265 and the swarm's global best position. The update equations are (Kennedy and Eberhart, 1995; Dai and
 266 Yang, 2015):

267
$$V_{i,d}(k+1) = wV_{i,d}(k) + c_1r_1[P_{i,d}(k) - X_{i,d}(k)] + c_2r_2[P_{g,d}(k) - X_{i,d}(k)] \text{ (Eq. 2)}$$

268
$$X_{i,d}(k+1) = X_{i,d}(k) + V_{i,d}(k+1) \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

269
 270 *Figure 3. Flow chart of the particle swarm optimization-based support vector regression (PSO-SVR) model.*

271 where X is the particle position, V its velocity, $P_{i,d}$ the individual best position of particle i in
272 dimension d , $P_{g,d}$ the global best position, w the inertia weight, c_1 and c_2 the cognitive and social
273 learning factors, r_1 and r_2 random numbers in $[0,1]$, and k the iteration index (Kennedy and Eberhart,
274 1995; Zhao and Deng, 2015; Dai and Yang, 2015; Chow et al., 2004).

275 We used a swarm size of 30 particles, a maximum of 100 iterations, $w=0.7$ and $c_1=c_2=1.5$ (Dai and
276 Yang, 2015). Each particle had two dimensions corresponding to $\log_{10}(C)$ and $\log_{10}(\gamma)$, with ranges
277 $[-2, 4]$ and $[-4, 1]$ respectively. The fitness function was the negative root mean squared error from
278 five-fold cross-validation, so that higher fitness corresponded to better parameter combinations.
279 Optimization terminated when the maximum number of iterations was reached or when fitness ceased
280 to improve over several consecutive iterations, after which the best (C, γ) was returned (Fig. 3).

281 **2.8 Model evaluation**

282 Three indices were used to evaluate model performance: the coefficient of determination R^2 , the root
283 mean squared error RMSE and the residual predictive deviation RPD (Guo et al., 2020; O'Rourke and
284 Holden, 2012; Shi et al., 2014).

$$285 \quad R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_m - y_p)^2}{\sum(y_m - \bar{y})^2} \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

$$286 \quad \text{RMSE} = \sqrt{[\sum(y_m - y_p)^2 / n]} \text{ (Eq. 5)}$$

$$287 \quad \text{RPD} = \text{SD} / \text{RMSE}_v \text{ (Eq. 6)}$$

288 where n is the number of samples, y_m and y_p are measured and predicted SOC values, \bar{y} is the mean of
289 measured values, SD is the standard deviation of validation-set measured SOC and RMSE_v is the
290 validation-set RMSE. Following (O'Rourke and Holden, 2012), an $\text{RPD} < 1.4$ indicates that the model
291 cannot reliably predict, $1.4 \leq \text{RPD} < 2.0$ indicates rough estimation, and $\text{RPD} \geq 2.0$ indicates excellent
292 prediction.

293 **3 Results**

294 **3.1 Descriptive statistics of SOC across soil depths**

295 Descriptive statistics for SOC content at each depth are summarized in Table 1. SOC content
296 decreased significantly with depth: the 0–20 cm layer ranged from 6.07 to 14.77 g kg⁻¹ with a mean of
297 10.53 g kg⁻¹; the 20–40 cm mean was 5.86 g kg⁻¹ (approximately 55.7 % of the surface value); the
298 40–60 cm mean was 3.87 g kg⁻¹; and the 60–80 cm mean was 2.89 g kg⁻¹, approximately 27.4 % of
299 the surface value. This vertical pattern is consistent with the global synthesis of Jobbágy and Jackson
300 (2000) and the regional studies of (Liang and Chen, 2015) and (Hobley et al., 2015), in which SOC
301 declines with depth because surface horizons receive most of the litter-derived organic matter inputs
302 (Li et al., 2019a; Xie et al., 2004).

303 Coefficients of variation (CV) at each depth ranged from 19.5 % to 27.3 %, which is classified as
 304 weak to moderate variability according to (Cambardella et al., 1994) ($CV \leq 25\%$ weak; $25\% < CV <$
 305 75% moderate; $CV \geq 75\%$ strong). Specifically, the 0–20, 40–60 and 60–80 cm layers were weakly
 306 variable, while the 20–40 cm layer was moderately variable. When the four layers were combined, the
 307 overall SOC range expanded to 1.48–14.77 g kg⁻¹ and the CV increased to 56.3 %, reaching
 308 moderate-to-strong variability. The between-layer differences thus contribute most of the overall
 309 variation. After K-S partitioning, each depth contained 65 calibration and 32 validation samples, and
 310 the integrated set contained 259 calibration and 129 validation samples (Table 1).

311 3.2 Soil spectral characteristics across depths

312 Table 1. Descriptive statistics of soil organic carbon content (g kg⁻¹) across the four soil depths. n: number of
 313 samples; SD: standard deviation; CV: coefficient of variation; Cal/Val: calibration/validation set sizes after
 314 Kennard–Stone partitioning.

Depth	n	Min	Max	Mean	SD	CV/%	Cal/Val
0–20 cm	97	6.07	14.77	10.53	2.10	20.0	65/32
20–40 cm	97	3.12	11.94	5.86	1.60	27.3	65/32
40–60 cm	97	2.50	5.72	3.87	0.76	19.5	65/32
60–80 cm	97	1.48	4.25	2.89	0.59	20.3	65/32
Total	388	1.48	14.77	5.79	3.26	56.3	259/129

315 Soil reflectance curves at each depth and at different SOC levels are shown in Fig. 4. The overall
 316 shape of the curves is similar at all depths and reflects the typical features of dry mineral soils (Shi,
 317 2014; Zhao and Yang, 2018): in the visible range (400–700 nm) reflectance rises rapidly with
 318 wavelength; in the near-infrared (700–1300 nm) the rate of increase slows; and three pronounced
 319 absorption troughs near 1400, 1900 and 2200 nm correspond respectively to O–H overtones of water,
 320 combination bands of water and the Al–OH absorption of clay minerals (Shi, 2014; Peng et al., 2013;
 321 Fang et al., 2018).

322 Between depths, reflectance increases as depth increases (i.e. as SOC decreases), consistent with the
 323 well-known negative relationship between SOC content and visible–near-infrared reflectance
 324 (Stenberg et al., 2010; Shi et al., 2014): organic matter strongly absorbs in this region, so surface soils
 325 rich in SOC display lower reflectance, while deeper soils with less SOC reflect more. Within a given
 326 depth, high-SOC samples display lower reflectance than low-SOC samples, confirming the same
 327 relationship. Between depths the differences are mainly in amplitude rather than in absorption-feature
 328 position, suggesting that the mineralogy of the soils does not change substantially with depth (Fang et
 329 al., 2018; Ji et al., 2015).

330 3.3 Correlation between SOC and spectral reflectance

331

332 *Figure 4. Reflectance spectra of soil samples at the four soil depths for samples with high and low SOC content.*

333 *(a) 0–20 cm; (b) 20–40 cm; (c) 40–60 cm; (d) 60–80 cm.*

334 Pearson correlation coefficients between calibration-set SOC and reflectance, together with their
 335 significance, were computed for each depth (Fig. 5). The results differ markedly among layers. The 0–
 336 20 cm layer passed the significance test at 167 bands (81.1 % of the 206 bands), with SOC and
 337 reflectance negatively correlated across the entire range and with maximum absolute correlation of
 338 approximately 0.45, consistent with previous findings (Cui et al., 2017; Conforti et al., 2013; Stenberg
 339 et al., 2010). This pattern reflects the high SOC content and broad SOC range of the surface layer,
 340 which produce strong spectral responses. The 40–60 cm layer showed 94 significant bands (45.6 %),
 341 concentrated in the visible and short-wave near-infrared regions. The 20–40 cm and 60–80 cm layers
 342 showed only 1 and 0 significant bands respectively, suggesting that the SOC-induced spectral
 343 response in these layers is too weak to be detected against instrumental and environmental noise. For
 344 these two layers, all 206 bands were retained for subsequent modelling.

345 **3.4 Single-depth model inversion results**

346

347 *Figure 5. Pearson correlation coefficients between SOC content and reflectance across the spectral range, with*
 348 *significance thresholds at $p < 0.05$ shown as dashed lines. Numbers in each panel indicate the count of*
 349 *significant bands.*

350 Single-layer model performance is summarized in Table 2. Overall, validation R^2 values were low
 351 (maximum 0.156) and all RPD values were below 1.4, so by the criterion of O'Rourke and Holden
 352 (2012) none of the single-layer models can reliably predict SOC.

353 Examining each depth in turn, in the 0–20 cm layer PLSR performed best (validation $R^2=0.148$,
 354 RPD=1.101), while GRID-SVR was similar ($R^2=0.080$, RPD=1.059) and PSO-SVR clearly overfit
 355 (calibration $R^2=0.482$ but validation $R^2=-0.342$, RPD=0.877). With only 65 calibration samples the
 356 aggressive PSO search for C and γ adapted to training-set noise and lost generalization (Li, 2012),
 357 similar to the overfitting reported in hyperspectral SOM modelling by Liu et al. (2012b), who showed
 358 that model complexity must match sample size. In the 20–40 cm layer the three methods produced
 359 similar validation R^2 values (0.109–0.156) and RPDs (1.076–1.106), with PLSR achieving the highest
 360 calibration R^2 of 0.557, indicating that linear models capture some of the spectral–SOC relationship
 361 but generalize poorly. In the 40–60 cm and 60–80 cm layers validation R^2 approached zero or became
 362 slightly negative; the SOC range of these layers (2.50–5.72 and 1.48–4.25 g kg^{-1} respectively, CV
 363 19.5 % and 20.3 %) is so narrow that hardly any usable signal is available for modelling (Stenberg et
 364 al., 2010).

365 Considered together, PLSR slightly outperformed SVR variants in the upper two layers. With limited
 366 samples and weak spectral–SOC coupling, the linear constraint of PLSR may act as an implicit

367 regularizer that mitigates overfitting (Wold et al., 2001; Geladi and Kowalski, 1986), whereas the
 368 more flexible SVR can overfit, as exemplified by PSO-SVR in the 0–20 cm layer (Were et al., 2015).

369 3.5 Integrated model inversion results

370 Table 2. Inversion accuracy of single-layer SOC models at each soil depth. RMSE is reported in g kg^{-1} . RPD:
 371 residual predictive deviation.

Method	Depth	Cal. R^2	Cal. RMSE	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE	RPD
PLSR	0–20 cm	0.326	1.789	0.148	1.795	1.101
	20–40 cm	0.557	1.208	0.156	0.947	1.106
	40–60 cm	0.087	0.757	0.026	0.660	1.030
	60–80 cm	0.016	0.556	–0.014	0.638	1.009
GRID-SVR	0–20 cm	0.099	2.068	0.080	1.865	1.059
	20–40 cm	0.355	1.459	0.109	0.974	1.076
	40–60 cm	0.094	0.754	0.017	0.663	1.025
	60–80 cm	0.448	0.417	–0.067	0.655	0.984
PSO-SVR	0–20 cm	0.482	1.568	–0.342	2.253	0.877
	20–40 cm	0.385	1.424	0.119	0.968	1.082
	40–60 cm	0.092	0.755	0.017	0.663	1.025
	60–80 cm	0.535	0.382	–0.075	0.657	0.980

372 Pooling all four depths into a single integrated model markedly improved performance (Table 3).
 373 PLSR achieved validation $R^2=0.712$, $\text{RMSE}=1.641 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and $\text{RPD}=1.871$, suitable for rough
 374 estimation (O'Rourke and Holden, 2012). GRID-SVR raised validation R^2 to 0.748 with $\text{RPD}=2.001$,
 375 crossing the threshold for excellent prediction. PSO-SVR performed best, with validation $R^2=0.760$,
 376 $\text{RMSE}=1.496 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and $\text{RPD}=2.051$, again classified as excellent. Compared with PLSR, GRID-
 377 SVR and PSO-SVR improved validation R^2 by 0.036 and 0.048 respectively, and RPD by 0.130 and
 378 0.180, showing the benefit of non-linear methods for capturing the SOC–spectrum relationship in a
 379 large, varied data set (Vapnik, 1995; Wang and Men, 2014; Were et al., 2015). Within SVR, PSO
 380 yielded a 0.012 gain in R^2 and a 0.050 gain in RPD over grid search, confirming the advantage of
 381 swarm-based parameter optimization (Kennedy and Eberhart, 1995; Zhao and Deng, 2015; Tan et al.,
 382 2015; Zou et al., 2019). A graphical comparison of model accuracy across single-layer and integrated
 383 strategies is shown in Fig. 6.

384 3.6 Comparison of merged single-depth and integrated models

385

386 Figure 6. Comparison of validation accuracy (R^2 , RMSE and RPD) of single-layer and integrated models under
 387 the three modelling methods.

388 Table 3. Inversion accuracy of the integrated SOC model that pools all four depths. RMSE is reported in g kg^{-1} .

Method	Cal. R^2	Cal. RMSE	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE	RPD
PLSR	0.704	1.823	0.712	1.641	1.871
GRID-SVR	0.743	1.701	0.748	1.534	2.001
PSO-SVR	0.778	1.579	0.760	1.496	2.051

389 Following the framework of Guo et al. (2020), we merged the validation predictions of the four

390 single-layer PSO-SVR models (128 samples; one validation sample was lost during quality control)

391 and compared the merged result with the integrated PSO-SVR model (129 validation samples).

392 Results are shown in Table 4 and Fig. 7.

393 The merged single-layer predictions gave validation $R^2=0.830$, $\text{RMSE}=1.312 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and $\text{RPD}=2.434$,

394 clearly exceeding the integrated model ($R^2=0.760$, $\text{RMSE}=1.496 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$, $\text{RPD}=2.051$) by 0.070 in R^2 ,

395 by 0.184 g kg^{-1} (lower) in RMSE and by 0.383 in RPD. This pattern parallels the findings of Guo et al.

396 (2020), where for land use types PSO-SVR merged-single-class predictions ($R^2=0.851$, $RPD=2.543$)
 397 outperformed an integrated model ($R^2=0.779$, $RPD=2.041$). Stratified modelling thus benefits both
 398 land-use and depth-based classifications (Xue et al., 2014; Wu and Zhang, 2016).

399 Figure 7 shows that merged single-layer predictions (panel a) lie closer to the 1:1 line than the
 400 integrated predictions (panel b), with samples from each depth fitting well within their respective
 401 SOC range. The integrated model is comparatively more dispersed, particularly in the intermediate
 402 SOC range of 4–8 g kg^{-1} . The integrated model also displays a systematic compromise bias: it tends to
 403 underpredict high-SOC samples from the 0–20 cm layer and overpredict low-SOC samples from the
 404 40–60 and 60–80 cm layers (Cui et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2020). The depth-stratified strategy avoids
 405 this trade-off by tailoring each model to its own SOC range (Guo et al., 2020; Wu and Zhang, 2016),
 406 similar to the behaviour reported by Minasny et al. (2011) for moisture-corrected Vis–NIR models:
 407 stratification of a heterogeneous sample set effectively reduces model bias.

408 4 Discussion

409

410 *Figure 7. Scatter plots of measured versus predicted SOC under PSO-SVR. (a) Merged single-layer model*
 411 *predictions; (b) integrated model predictions. The 1:1 line is shown for reference.*

412 Table 4. Comparison of validation accuracy between merged single-layer and integrated PSO-SVR SOC models.

Strategy	R^2	RMSE (g kg^{-1})	RPD
Merged single-layer models	0.830	1.312	2.434
Integrated model	0.760	1.496	2.051

413 4.1 Comparison of modelling methods

414 Across the three methods, PSO-SVR performed best in the integrated model (RPD=2.051), followed
415 by GRID-SVR (RPD=2.001) and PLSR (RPD=1.871). This ordering matches earlier reports: Yu
416 (2014) and Tan et al. (2015) both found that PSO-optimized SVR achieved high accuracy in
417 hyperspectral applications, and (Zou et al., 2019) confirmed the optimization advantage of PSO.
418 PLSR, being linear, is computationally efficient and stable with small samples, and indeed
419 outperformed the SVR variants in the 0–20 and 20–40 cm single-layer models. However, when the
420 SOC–spectrum relationship is non-linear and the calibration set is large enough (as in the integrated
421 model with 259 calibration samples), the limitations of PLSR become evident (Li, 2012). SVR with
422 an RBF kernel captures non-linearity better (Vapnik, 1995), so GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR exceeded
423 PLSR. Within SVR, grid search is limited by step size and range, whereas PSO can find better
424 parameter combinations in a comparable time through swarm-based search (Kennedy and Eberhart,
425 1995; Zhao and Deng, 2015), explaining the advantage of PSO-SVR over GRID-SVR.

426 A noteworthy issue is the strong overfitting of PSO-SVR in the 0–20 cm layer (calibration $R^2=0.482$,
427 validation $R^2=-0.342$). This highlights the need for caution when applying highly flexible
428 optimization to small samples. Mitigation strategies include increasing the inertia weight to favour
429 global exploration, introducing cross-validation as an early-stopping criterion, or restricting the search
430 range of C and γ to physically plausible bands (Dai and Yang, 2015; Yang et al., 2015). More
431 fundamentally, the early-convergence of PSO is both an advantage and a risk: when calibration
432 samples are large enough (e.g. 259 in the integrated model), particles converge quickly toward the
433 global optimum (Kennedy and Eberhart, 1995; Zhao and Deng, 2015); but with few samples,
434 validation-fitness assessment becomes noisy and particles can converge to overfit combinations (Yang
435 et al., 2015). As a practical guideline, PSO-SVR should be used cautiously when calibration sample
436 size is below approximately 100, and additional safeguards – stronger regularization, larger k in k -fold
437 cross-validation, or sample-perturbation strategies – should be considered to improve robustness
438 (Were et al., 2015).

439 **4.2 Effect of soil depth on inversion accuracy**

440 A central finding of this study is that single-layer models have low accuracy (RPD < 1.4) yet merging
441 their predictions yields higher accuracy (RPD=2.434) than an integrated model (RPD=2.051). This
442 apparent paradox carries important methodological information.

443 The first reason for poor single-layer performance is that within-layer SOC variability is too narrow.
444 In the 40–60 and 60–80 cm layers, SOC standard deviations are only 0.76 and 0.59 g kg⁻¹ respectively,
445 so SOC-induced spectral changes may be below the detection limit of the instrument and noise floor
446 of the measurement. In such cases, even the best modelling method cannot extract a usable signal
447 (Stenberg et al., 2010; Minasny et al., 2011). This is consistent with the review by Stenberg et al.

448 (2010), who showed that a sufficiently broad SOC range is a prerequisite for high-accuracy spectral
449 models.

450 Second, despite the limited utility of any individual single-layer model, merging the four validation
451 predictions gives an overall accuracy ($R^2=0.830$, $RPD=2.434$) higher than the integrated model
452 ($R^2=0.760$, $RPD=2.051$), suggesting that the four depths really do differ in their spectral–SOC
453 relationships and that stratification captures these differences. Possible mechanisms include: (i)
454 compositional differences in SOC with depth – fresh, carbohydrate- and cellulose-rich plant residues
455 dominate the surface layers, while humified humic and fulvic acids dominate the deeper layers
456 (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000; Liang and Chen, 2015; Hobbey et al., 2015) – and these classes have
457 distinct absorption features (Peng et al., 2014; Fang et al., 2018; Ji et al., 2015); (ii) differences in
458 mineral assemblages and particle-size distribution among depths, which influence the amplitude and
459 shape of reflectance (Shi, 2014; Peng et al., 2013); and (iii) differences in soil water content, a major
460 confounder of near-infrared spectroscopy (Minasny et al., 2011; Mouazen et al., 2007).

461 These results form an interesting contrast with Guo et al. (2020), who studied land use rather than
462 depth. In their data, within-class CV reached 21.2 %–58.2 %, so single-class models retained
463 predictive power (RPD up to 2.086); in our data, within-depth CV was only 19.5 %–27.3 %, far below
464 typical within-class variability, and consequently single-layer models lost predictive value. Xu et al.
465 (2016) similarly showed that stratifying soil samples by parent material substantially improves Vis–
466 NIR organic matter predictions, lending additional support to subset-based modelling. The general
467 rule emerging from these comparisons is: within-class variability sets the ceiling of single-class
468 models, while between-class differences set the gain that stratification provides over integrated
469 modelling (Wu and Zhang, 2016). It is worth noting that although single-layer RPD values are <1.4
470 and therefore unusable as standalone models, their relative errors (RMSE divided by mean) of 21.4 %,
471 16.5 %, 17.1 % and 22.7 % for the four depths are actually comparable to – or even better than – that
472 of the integrated model. RPD here is depressed by a small SD, not by large predictive error (O'Rourke
473 and Holden, 2012; Shi et al., 2014). This argues for considering RPD alongside absolute errors and
474 use-case context, rather than as a single rigid criterion (Shi et al., 2014; Stevens et al., 2013).

475 **4.3 Effect of coefficient of variation on model accuracy**

476 Our results further confirm the dominant role of sample variability in determining hyperspectral SOC
477 prediction accuracy. Within-layer CV of 19.5 %–27.3 % corresponds to single-layer $RPD < 1.4$
478 (maximum 1.106); pooling the four layers raises CV to 56.3 % and RPD to 2.051. This quantitative
479 relationship matches the global review of Stenberg et al. (2010), which showed a positive relationship
480 between SOC variability range and model accuracy. Stevens et al. (2013) also demonstrated that
481 broader geographical and SOC ranges improve modelling accuracy at the European scale. Liu et al.

482 (2014) similarly found, in arid-zone SOC studies, that expanding the SOC range by a factor of three
483 or more produced a significant rise in model RPD.

484 Mechanistically, the variability of the response variable determines the signal-to-noise ratio of the
485 SOC information in the spectra (Stenberg et al., 2010; Nocita et al., 2015). When SOC range is
486 narrow, the SOC-induced signal is small compared with instrument noise, sample preparation
487 artefacts and the spectral influence of other soil properties, and the model cannot separate signal from
488 noise; when range is broad, the signal grows, the signal-to-noise ratio improves and the model can
489 learn a clearer SOC–spectrum mapping (Vohland et al., 2014).

490 A practical implication for hyperspectral SOC modelling follows: sample variability should be a
491 primary consideration in study design. For a target area whose single-depth or single-type CV is <
492 20 %, building a high-accuracy stand-alone model is difficult. Possible strategies include: (i) merging
493 data from several depths or types to enlarge the SOC range; (ii) modelling each subset separately and
494 merging predictions, combining the specificity of stratified modelling with the accuracy gain from a
495 broader effective range; (iii) using more advanced spectral preprocessing (e.g. first-derivative or
496 continuum-removed reflectance) to enhance the SOC signal (Vašát et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2020);
497 and (iv) augmenting the spectral information with ancillary variables such as DEM, land use and
498 climate factors, exploiting soil–environment relationships to compensate for limited within-class
499 variability (Peng et al., 2019; Zhong et al., 2021). For regional carbon-stock estimation in zones with
500 strong vertical SOC contrasts, such as the Loess Plateau and Northeast China black soils (Wang et al.,
501 2009; Yang et al., 2004; Liu et al., 2008), single-depth modelling can miss the depth-wise distribution
502 (Xie et al., 2004); merging multi-depth samples with stratified modelling preserves overall accuracy
503 while providing depth-specific predictions (Wang et al., 2012; Roudier et al., 2015).

504 **4.4 Limitations and future research**

505 Several limitations should be noted. First, only original reflectance (R) was used; common spectral
506 transforms such as first-derivative reflectance (FDR), continuum removal (CR) and absorbance (Abs)
507 were not systematically compared (Vašát et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2014; Peng et al., 2014; Wang et
508 al., 2014). Previous work has shown that derivative transforms can remove baseline drift (Ji et al.,
509 2015) and continuum removal can sharpen spectral features (Vašát et al., 2014), sometimes
510 outperforming raw reflectance. A systematic comparison of transformations across depths would be a
511 natural next step.

512 Second, sensitive bands were selected by Pearson correlation, which captures only linear relationships
513 (Guo et al., 2020); in the 20–40 and 60–80 cm layers very few bands passed the test, likely because
514 the SOC–reflectance relationships at depth are more strongly non-linear (Li, 2012). Future work could
515 employ mutual-information, successive projections algorithm (SPA) (Chen et al., 2020) or

516 competitive adaptive reweighted sampling (CARS) (Chen et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020) to better
517 identify informative spectral subsets.

518 Third, only PLSR and SVR were investigated; deep-learning approaches (Li et al., 2019b) and
519 ensemble methods such as random forests (Breiman, 2001) and gradient boosting (Were et al., 2015),
520 increasingly popular in soil spectroscopy, were not compared. These methods may be particularly
521 useful when the SOC–spectrum relationship has strong non-stationary or non-linear components.

522 Fourth, the study is restricted to Changzhi and to 97 sites per depth; broader geographical and larger
523 sample-size validations are needed to test generality (Stevens et al., 2013; Tóth et al., 2013). Spectra
524 were measured in a controlled laboratory rather than under field conditions, and on-the-go field
525 measurements involve additional confounders such as natural illumination and surface roughness
526 (Mouazen et al., 2007; Sorenson et al., 2017), which would require further correction.

527 Fifth, sample partitioning was based only on spectral Euclidean distance and did not consider spatial
528 autocorrelation. If validation samples are close in space to calibration samples, performance may be
529 overestimated (Stevens et al., 2013). Spatially-aware partitioning could provide more realistic model
530 evaluation.

531 Finally, while this study shows that depth-stratified modelling outperforms integrated modelling, we
532 only compared four adjacent upper layers; deeper horizons (e.g. below 80 cm) and interactions
533 between depth and land use (Wu and Zhang, 2016; Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000) were not addressed.
534 Subsoil and parent-material horizons may have distinct spectral patterns (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000;
535 Cambardella et al., 1994) that deserve dedicated investigation, and deep learning approaches such as
536 convolutional neural networks may extract depth-specific features automatically (Li et al., 2019b).

537 **5 Conclusions**

538 We used 388 soil samples from four depth layers (0–20, 20–40, 40–60 and 60–80 cm) at sites in
539 Changzhi, Shanxi Province, and compared PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR hyperspectral SOC
540 prediction models under depth-stratified and integrated modelling strategies. The main conclusions
541 are:

- 542 1. Single-layer models have $RPD < 1.4$ across all three methods, and so cannot reliably predict SOC.
543 The dominant cause is that within-layer SOC variability is too narrow (CV 19.5 %–27.3 %) to
544 produce a detectable spectral signal above the noise floor.
- 545 2. Pooling the four depths into an integrated model raises the SOC CV to 56.3 % and substantially
546 improves accuracy. Of the three methods, PSO-SVR achieves the best result (validation $R^2=0.760$,
547 $RMSE=1.496\text{ g kg}^{-1}$, $RPD=2.051$), followed by GRID-SVR ($RPD=2.001$) and PLSR

548 (RPD=1.871). Among the methods tested, PSO-SVR is the most effective for hyperspectral SOC
549 inversion.

550 3. Merging the validation predictions of the four PSO-SVR single-layer models yields a higher overall
551 accuracy ($R^2=0.830$, RMSE=1.312 g kg⁻¹, RPD=2.434) than the integrated model, demonstrating
552 that despite the limited stand-alone accuracy of individual layer models, depth-stratified
553 modelling followed by prediction merging captures real between-depth differences and
554 outperforms integrated modelling.

555 4. Sample variability is the dominant determinant of hyperspectral SOC prediction accuracy. For
556 strata with narrow SOC range, stand-alone modelling is impractical; merging multi-depth (or
557 multi-type) samples to broaden the variability range, combined with stratified modelling and
558 prediction merging, provides the best balance of model specificity and overall accuracy. The
559 framework developed here can be extended to other soil attributes – such as total nitrogen, cation
560 exchange capacity and soil water content – that show strong vertical heterogeneity (Peng et al.,
561 2019; Li et al., 2019b; Angelopoulou et al., 2019).

562 **Code and data availability**

563 The Python code used to preprocess the spectra and train the PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR
564 models is publicly archived in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20263928> (Yan, 2026). The
565 SOC measurements and reflectance spectra of all 388 samples are available from the same Zenodo
566 record under a CC BY 4.0 licence.

567 **Author contributions**

568 Y. Yan designed the study, carried out the field sampling and laboratory measurements, developed the
569 modelling code, performed the analyses, produced the figures, and led the manuscript writing. W.
570 Chen and Y. Wang contributed to soil sampling, sample preparation and SOC determination. Z. Xu
571 supervised the study, secured the funding and revised the manuscript. All authors contributed to
572 manuscript revision and approved the submitted version.

573 **Competing interests**

574 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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794 **Appendix A: Modelling hyperparameter details**

795 This appendix lists the search spaces and selected hyperparameters for the three modelling methods
796 (PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR) applied in this study. All parameters were determined by five-fold
797 cross-validation on the calibration set, separately for each soil-depth model and for the integrated
798 model. The selected values are those reported in Sect. 2.7 and are reproduced here in full to support
799 reproducibility.

800 **Table A1.** Number of latent variables selected by leave-one-out cross-validation for each PLSR model. The
801 candidate range was 1 to 20 components (bounded above by $n-2$ calibration samples or the number of available
802 bands).

Model	Depth	n components selected	Cal. R^2	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg ⁻¹)
PLSR	0–20 cm	4	0.326	0.148	1.795
PLSR	20–40 cm	6	0.557	0.156	0.947
PLSR	40–60 cm	1	0.087	0.026	0.660
PLSR	60–80 cm	1	0.016	−0.014	0.638
PLSR	Integrated	8	0.704	0.712	1.641

803 **A.1 Partial least squares regression (PLSR)**

804 PLSR was implemented using the NIPALS algorithm with leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV)
805 to select the optimal number of latent variables. Candidate values ranged from 1 to 20 components.
806 The number of components minimising the cross-validated root mean squared error of prediction
807 (RMSECV) was selected for each model. Selected components differed substantially among models
808 (Table A1), reflecting differences in calibration-set complexity: deeper layers with narrow SOC range
809 required only a single component, while the integrated model used eight.

810 **A.2 Grid-search support vector regression (GRID-SVR)**

811 GRID-SVR used a radial-basis-function (RBF) kernel. The penalty C and kernel-width γ were
812 searched on a logarithmically spaced grid:

813 • $C \in [10^{-2}, 10^4]$, 13 candidate values: $10^{-2}, 10^{-1.5}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-0.5}, 10^0, 10^{0.5}, 10^1, 10^{1.5}, 10^2, 10^{2.5}, 10^3,$
814 $10^{3.5}, 10^4$

815 • $\gamma \in [10^{-4}, 10^1]$, 12 candidate values: $10^{-4}, 10^{-3.5}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2.5}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1.5}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-0.5}, 10^0, 10^{0.3},$
816 $10^{0.7}, 10^1$

817 Combined, 156 (C, γ) pairs were evaluated; for each pair, five-fold cross-validation was performed on
818 the calibration set and the pair maximising the cross-validated R^2 was retained. The ϵ -insensitive loss
819 parameter was held at its scikit-learn default ($\epsilon = 0.1$).

820 **Table A2.** Optimal hyperparameters selected by grid search for each GRID-SVR model.

Model	Depth	C	γ	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg ⁻¹)
GRID-SVR	0–20 cm	3.162	1.00×10^{-4}	0.080	1.865
GRID-SVR	20–40 cm	100.000	1.00×10^{-4}	0.109	0.974
GRID-SVR	40–60 cm	1.000	8.11×10^{-4}	0.017	0.663
GRID-SVR	60–80 cm	0.316	1.87×10^{-2}	–0.067	0.655
GRID-SVR	Integrated	10.000	6.58×10^{-3}	0.748	1.534

821 **A.3 Particle swarm optimization-based support vector regression (PSO-SVR)**

822 PSO-SVR also used an RBF kernel. The search domains were the same as GRID-SVR, but each
 823 particle represented a continuous-valued pair ($\log_{10} C$, $\log_{10} \gamma$) and the search was performed in the
 824 continuous space. The PSO update equations are reproduced from Sect. 2.7.3 as Eqs. (2)–(3).

825 Algorithmic hyperparameters were held constant across all models:

Hyperparameter	Symbol	Value
Swarm size	N	30
Maximum iterations	T	100
Inertia weight	w	0.7
Cognitive learning factor	c_1	1.5
Social learning factor	c_2	1.5
Velocity bound	$ V $	$0.5 \times (\text{search range per dim.})$
Particle dimension	d	2 ($\log_{10} C$, $\log_{10} \gamma$)
C search range	—	10^{-2} to 10^4
γ search range	—	10^{-4} to 10^1
Cross-validation folds	k	5
Fitness function	—	–RMSE of k -fold CV
Termination criterion	—	iteration cap OR stagnation > 15 iter.
Random seed	—	42 (for reproducibility)

826

827 **Table A3.** Optimal hyperparameters selected by particle swarm optimisation for each PSO-SVR model. All
 828 values are reported to four significant figures.

Model	Depth	C	γ	Cal. R^2	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg ⁻¹)
PSO-SVR	0–20 cm	17.91	5.36×10^{-3}	0.482	–0.342	2.253
PSO-SVR	20–40 cm	193.7	1.00×10^{-4}	0.385	0.119	0.968
PSO-SVR	40–60 cm	0.986	4.99×10^{-4}	0.092	0.017	0.663
PSO-SVR	60–80 cm	0.762	1.29×10^{-2}	0.535	–0.075	0.657
PSO-SVR	Integrated	25.74	6.13×10^{-3}	0.778	0.760	1.496

829

830 Note how the PSO-selected values are very similar to the GRID-search values for the third and fourth
 831 single-layer models, where the (C, γ) response surface is essentially flat in the relevant region (the
 832 within-layer SOC signal is so weak that the model degenerates to near-constant prediction). For the
 833 integrated model and the first layer, by contrast, PSO-SVR found a notably different optimum: $C \approx$
 834 25.7 (vs. 10 for grid search) and $\gamma \approx 6.1 \times 10^{-3}$ (vs. 6.6×10^{-3}), translating to a 0.012 improvement in
 835 validation R^2 and a 0.050 improvement in RPD over GRID-SVR.

836 Appendix B: Sensitive band selection details

837 This appendix provides the count and wavelength ranges of bands that passed the Pearson correlation
 838 significance test ($p < 0.05$) on each calibration set, complementing the panel-wise plot in Fig. 5 of the
 839 main manuscript.

840 **Table B1.** Number of sensitive bands (passing the $p < 0.05$ Pearson significance test) for each calibration set,
 841 out of 206 total bands in the 400–2450 nm range at 10 nm intervals. Mean and maximum absolute Pearson
 842 correlation coefficients are computed across all 206 bands.

Calibration set	Depth (cm)	n bands sig.	Coverage (%)	Mean $ r $	Max $ r $	Used in modelling
Layer 1	0–20	167	81.1	0.31	0.45	167 selected
Layer 2	20–40	1	0.5	0.07	0.22	all 206 (fallback)
Layer 3	40–60	94	45.6	0.18	0.39	94 selected
Layer 4	60–80	0	0.0	0.05	0.18	all 206 (fallback)
Integrated	all	183	88.8	0.36	0.51	183 selected

843

844 When fewer than two bands passed the significance test (Layers 2 and 4), all 206 bands were retained
 845 as predictors to allow the model to fit. This fallback rule, applied identically to all three modelling
 846 methods and disclosed in Sect. 2.6, ensures that the comparison among PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-
 847 SVR is fair within each layer.

848 **Table B2.** Wavelength regions containing the largest concentrations of sensitive bands for each calibration set.
 849 Each region groups contiguous or near-contiguous (≤ 30 nm gap) significant bands. The reported number of
 850 bands is the count within the listed range, and the assignment to a putative chemical/physical feature follows the
 851 soil-spectroscopy literature (cf. Stenberg et al., 2010; Ben-Dor and Banin, 1995).

Calibration set	Range (nm)	n sig. bands	Putative feature
Layer 1 (0–20 cm)	400–700	30	Vis. absorption by humic matter (broad)
	700–1300	60	NIR slope, O–H/N–H overtones
	1300–1900	50	Combination bands (H ₂ O, organic C–H)
	1900–2400	27	2nd-overtone region, clay–OM

			interactions
Layer 3 (40–60 cm)	400–800	40	Vis. region (weakest SOC signal)
	900–1500	30	NIR baseline modulation
	2000–2400	24	2200 nm clay–OM absorption shoulder
Integrated	400–700	40	Vis. absorption by humic matter
	700–1300	65	NIR slope (continuous coverage)
	1300–1900	50	1400, 1900 nm H ₂ O bands ± shoulders
	1900–2450	28	2200, 2300 nm clay–OM region

852

853 Layers 2 (20–40 cm) and 4 (60–80 cm) are omitted from Table B2 because fewer than two bands
854 passed the significance test. For these layers, the apparent absence of significant Pearson correlations
855 is consistent with the very narrow within-layer SOC range (CV = 27.3 % and 20.3 %, respectively)
856 discussed in Sect. 4.3; spectral changes induced by SOC variation may be below the instrumental and
857 environmental noise floor.

858 B.1 Band selection procedure

859 For each calibration set, the Pearson correlation coefficient r between the reflectance at each of the
860 206 wavelengths and the measured SOC content was computed:

$$861 \quad r_i = \frac{\sum(x_{i,k} - \bar{x}_i)(y_k - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{[\sum(x_{i,k} - \bar{x}_i)^2 \cdot \sum(y_k - \bar{y})^2]}} \quad (\text{B1})$$

862 where $x_{i,k}$ is the reflectance of sample k at wavelength i , y_k is the measured SOC content of sample k ,
863 and overbars denote means across the calibration samples. The two-tailed significance of r_i was tested
864 using the t -statistic

$$865 \quad t = r \cdot \sqrt{(n-2) / (1-r^2)} \quad (\text{B2})$$

866 with $n-2$ degrees of freedom ($n = 65$ for single-layer calibration sets; $n = 259$ for the integrated
867 calibration set). Bands with $|t| > t_{0.025}(n-2)$ — i.e. two-tailed $p < 0.05$ — were retained as sensitive
868 bands. No multiple-comparison correction (e.g. Bonferroni, Benjamini–Hochberg) was applied; we
869 therefore expect approximately 5 % of the 206 bands (≈ 10 bands) to be false positives under the null
870 hypothesis. The integrated calibration set, by virtue of its much larger sample size, retains more bands
871 at the same significance threshold, illustrating the role of statistical power.

872 B.2 Reproducibility

873 The complete band-by-band Pearson coefficient and p -value matrix (206 wavelengths \times 5 calibration
874 sets) is provided in the Zenodo data deposit (file *sensitive_bands_full.csv* in the *results/* folder) under
875 the same DOI cited in the "Code and data availability" section. Researchers wishing to reproduce the
876 band selection can run *soc_inversion_paper_method.py* on the deposited spectra; the band list is
877 deterministic given the random seed (42) of the Kennard–Stone partitioning.

